

EduLiM Project

“Educational Transitions in the Context of Linguistic Minoritization”

WP3 (Sub-project B)

Data Management Plan

Version 1

Progetto finanziato dalla Provincia Autonoma di Bolzano - Ripartizione Innovazione, Ricerca, Università e Musei nell'ambito del Programma Research Südtirol/Alto Adige 2022

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Table of Contents

1	Project Information	4
2	Data summary.....	5
2.1	Data description and collection.....	5
2.1.1	Sources of data.....	6
2.1.2	Data collection process.....	7
2.2	Format and size of data.....	8
3	Data storage and back-up.....	9
3.1	Data de-identification	9
3.1.1	Pseudonymization and anonymization	9
3.2	Storage and back-up	12
3.3	Folder structures and file naming	12
3.3.1	Main Folder Structure.....	12
3.3.2	Subfolders.....	13
4	Data documentation.....	13
4.1	Data consistency and quality control	13
	Metadata.....	14
5	Data access	14
5.1	Copyright and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR)	14
5.2	Data access and sharing	15
5.3	Data access in case of staff changes.....	15
6	Data storage and preservation	16
6.1	Criteria for long-term preservation	16
7	Legal and ethical considerations	16
8	Resources and costs	17

1 Project Information

Name of the project	Education Transitions in the Context of Linguistic Minoritization (EduLiM)
Description of the project	<p>Abstract</p> <p>The project <i>Educational Transitions in the Context of Linguistic Minoritization</i> examines the role of language in children’s transition from early childhood education to primary school in the context of German-language education in South Tyrol. Language plays a central role in educational transitions as it can facilitate or hinder access to educational spaces and is thus implicated in the reproduction of social inequality. The project combines critical educational and sociolinguistic theories and is designed as a multi-sited ethnography conducted in first-year primary school classes and with children’s families. Two subprojects are implemented and coordinated respectively by the University of Innsbruck (schools) and Eurac Research (families). In this way, EduLiM aims to create new knowledge on (language) education policies and practices related to transitions, on collaboration across institutional boundaries and between families and institutions, and on different ways in which children are constructed as linguistically minoritized. More specifically, the project may contribute to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Further theory-building on linguistic minoritization in educational transitions and in education more generally; - Methodological and ethical discussions on multilingualism in the collection and analysis of data; - Language education policy and pedagogical professionalization in line with current socio-political challenges; - Developing a theory-practice cooperation with all relevant stakeholders in South Tyrol. <p>Research Question(s)</p> <p>The interdisciplinary project EduLiM adopts an ethnographical approach through a multi-sited ethnography – i.e., the co-existence of diverse (physical) sites in the research design. This methodology is directed towards relations between individual actors (children, parents, pedagogical professionals, etc.) in different social settings. Generalization of the findings is not based on statistical significance but on theoretical representativeness. EduLiM addresses the following overarching research questions:</p> <p>RQ1: Which transitional practices can be observed in preschool-school-transitions in South Tyrol?</p> <p>RQ2: How is language made salient in these practices by different actors (teachers, children, parents and other actors in school and family)?</p> <p>RQ3: How are transitional practices in the school and in families informed by normative framings and ideologies about language and education?</p> <p>For the part of the project undertaken at Eurac Research, the following research questions are formulated:</p> <p>RQ 1.B: Which transitional practices can be observed in families with a child that transitions out from a German-language preschool and/or into a German-language primary school?</p> <p>RQ 2.B: How is language made salient in these practices throughout the transition process?</p> <p>RQ 3.B: How are transitional practices in the family informed by normative framings and ideologies about language and education?</p>

	The site is composed of six selected families with at least one preschool child who will transition to school in the following school year. Qualitative interviews will be conducted with relevant actors (children, teachers, parents, etc.) in addition to participant observations to be able to relate different perspectives to one another. Participant observation will be documented with fieldnotes, audio recordings and other research artifacts – e.g., pictures of places, objects and people without showing their faces. Fieldwork will begin once research relations are established with families and intensify around transition-relevant phases before school starts (e.g., school choice and enrollment) as well as in the months around and after the child's transition to school.
Funding body	Province of Bolzano – Legge 14/2006
Project ID	CUP D53C24000290003
Partner Institution	University of Innsbruck
Duration	36 months Start date: June 2024
Consortium, Participants, roles, stakeholders	<i>Staff at Eurac Research</i> Giorgia Andreoli, Co-Principal Investigator https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9511-0496 Safà El Koura, PhD Student <i>Partner (Leading) institution</i> Nadja Thoma, Principal Investigator https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9084-9638 Kristina Savic, PhD Student Safà El Koura, PhD Student
Date DMP created	05.02.2025
Date DMP (last) update	19.06.2025
Research organization registry (ROR)	Eurac Research - Institute for applied linguistics: https://ror.org/05rxnta87

2 Data summary

2.1 Data description and collection

EduLiM investigates transitional practices in the context of preschool-school-transitions in South Tyrol. Eurac Research is responsible for sub-project B, which involves a multi-sited ethnography with families with at least one child transitioning from pre-school to primary school as well as key informants. EduLiM employs fieldwork methods consisting of participant observation and ethnographic interviews. Therefore, EduLiM uses primary data, i.e., data generated from the multi-sited ethnography (such as field notes and interviews).

2.1.1 Sources of data

Data is collected individually by the project co-PI and project employed staff. EduLiM uses two types of data:

- Primary data, generated from ethnographic fieldwork (participant observation) and interviews (data type A);
- Secondary data, i.e., scholarly articles and publications employed in the project literature review; grey literature, e.g. policy and curriculum documentation relevant to the project (data type B).

(A) Primary data:

Source of data: data collected by the project Co-PI and the PhD Student during ethnographic fieldwork.

Types of data:

- **A1:** contact details of participants
- **A2:** participants' categorization (personal data, incl. of special categories, e.g., on ethnic origins; reference to art. 9 EU Regulation 2016/679 - GDPR)
- **A3:** audio data consisting of recordings of ethnographic fieldwork (participant observation) and interview data
- **A4:** textual data consisting of ethnographic field notes written by the researchers during and after participant observation and interview transcripts (raw data: field notes and transcripts; elaborated data: notes and interpretations, coded data)
- **A5:** photographs taken by the researchers and by the participants during fieldwork and interviews
- **A6:** research artifacts handwritten or drawn by the participants, e.g., notes, drawings, language portraits

(B) Secondary data:

Source of data: data collected by the project Co-PI, the PhD Student employed by Eurac Research and other research staff employed by Eurac or the University of Innsbruck, including: open access articles or articles that may be retrieved via institutional libraries; online portals of the Autonomous Province of Bolzano/Bozen and other local agencies; websites of local schools.

Types of data:

- **B1:** research articles, manuscripts, and other research outputs for the purposes of literature review
- **B2:** other relevant documentation, e.g., policies, administrative documentation, curricula and school documentation, webpages, blog articles

2.1.2 Data collection process

- **A1.** Contacts are provided by participants or key informants. If a participant decides to opt out of the project, their data will be immediately destroyed.
- **A1 and A2.** During fieldwork (i.e., participant observation and interviews), the informants/participants may provide information about their name and surname, ethnic origins, languages, gender, residence and domicile, religion, geographical origins, and work and volunteering affiliations. Given the emergent nature of ethnographic work, rooted in the construction of a safe and trusted space with the families, sensitive information may be disclosed. However, this will be done at the participant's discretion and is foreseen by the consent form. Examples of such information include (but may not be limited to): the schools attended by the children, trajectories of migration, lived experiences of discrimination, political opinions, sexual orientation, criminal offences, etc. Such data may be included in A3 and A4.
- **A3 and A4.** During fieldwork, researchers take notes and audio record interactions for both participant observation and ethnographic interviews. Field notes are also elaborated in a diary form by the researchers after the fieldwork, typically within 48 hours. Audio recordings are transcribed manually or using [aTrain – Transcription tool for qualitative research](#). Elaborated data are de-identified and interpreted during data interpretation sessions with the project staff and analyzed using a computer-assisted qualitative data analysis software (CAQDAS).
- **A5 and A6.** Photographs, drawings and other research artifacts are collected during fieldwork and stored in a digital format. Photos of participants are taken with their consent and do not show faces or any immediately recognizable features.
- **B1 and B2.** The literature review (B1) will be based on published scholarship accessed either freely (i.e., Open Access) or retrieved via the libraries of Eurac Research and the University of Innsbruck. Emails may be sent to individual authors if their articles are not available through these channels. Other documentation (B2) normally takes the form of freely downloadable documents or webpages (e.g., policies, administrative documentation, school curricula and regulations).

2.1.2.1 Particular character of data

A1-A6 data may contain not only personal but also special categories of personal data (e.g., on ethnic origins, sexual orientation, and political beliefs) in accordance with art. 9 EU Regulation 2016/679 – GDPR. Data type A1, A2 and A3 will be deleted after the completion of the project. The elaborated data of types A3-A6 will be retained up to 10 years after the completion of the project in accordance with the project information and privacy sheet distributed to the participants and that contains also the consent forms as specified below. B1 and B2 do not contain special categories of personal data.

2.1.2.2 Consent procedures

Prior to data collection of data A2-A6, each participant receives an information notice containing details about the EduLiM project and its methodology, research techniques and results, and on the data protection and privacy and the processing of the participant's personal data in accordance with EU Regulation 2016/679 (GDPR), incl., art. 9 on special categories of personal data (such as those on ethnic origins). The information notice also includes consent forms, which are signed voluntarily by participants and specify: consent to the processing of personal data (including, as mentioned, special categories such as those on the ethnic origins), permission to the project team to take pictures (without including participants' faces) and audio recordings for transcription purposes, and the right to withdraw from the project and revoke the consent at any time. The information notice and the consent forms are elaborated in cooperation with Eurac Research Legal Office that ensures the respect of all national, European, and international laws. The Co-PI is responsible for handing in such information notice and collecting signed consent forms from each participant before involving them in any project activity. Consent forms will be scanned and stored in Eurac infrastructure and retained for 10 years after the

project in accordance with the project information and privacy sheet, after which date they will be destroyed. If sent via email, the emails containing the consent form will be destroyed once the scanned file is stored. Hardcopies will be destroyed at the end of the project and, until then, stored at Eurac's archives.

2.2 Format and size of data

Data type	Format	Software	Estimated size	GDPR
A1 and A2	.csv	Excel	100 kb	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Contain personal data <input type="checkbox"/> May contain special categories (art. 9 GDPR) <input type="checkbox"/> Do not contain personal data
A3	Audio files (.mp3, .wma, .wav) CAQDAS project files (to be defined)	PC, audio recorders, aTrain, media player	20 GB	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Contain personal data <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> May contain special categories (art. 9 GDPR) <input type="checkbox"/> Do not contain personal data
A4	Text files (.doc, .docx, .rtf, .txt, .pdf, .json, .srt) CAQDAS project files (to be defined)	PC, Word processor, aTrain, CAQDAS software	10 GB	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Contain personal data <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> May contain special categories (art. 9 GDPR) <input type="checkbox"/> Do not contain personal data
A5 and A6	Image files (.bmp, .gif, .jpg, .jpeg, .tif, .tiff) Text files (.doc, .docx, .rtf, .txt, .pdf, .json, .srt) CAQDAS project files (to be defined)	PC, Eurac/own camera, Photos app, CAQDAS software	5 GB	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Contain personal data <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> May contain special categories (art. 9 GDPR) <input type="checkbox"/> Do not contain personal data
B1, B2	Text files (.doc, .docx, .rtf, .txt, .pdf) Image files (.bmp, .gif, .jpg, .jpeg, .tif, .tiff) CAQDAS project files (to be defined)	PC, Word, pdf reader, Photos app, CAQDAS software	5 GB	<input type="checkbox"/> Contain personal data (GDPR) <input type="checkbox"/> May contain special categories (art. 9 GDPR) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Do not contain personal data
<i>Estimated total space required</i>			40 GB	

3 Data storage and back-up

3.1 Data de-identification

Data de-identification is not seen as one specific moment but rather an ongoing process, which is discussed within the project staff and highly dependent upon other contextual information. There are no plans to make the data openly available. However, de-identification is necessary at different levels and may also involve shorter data extracts shared within project staff for the purposes of data analysis or included in publications. Ethnographic data can be anonymized in certain cases but will more often be pseudonymized or anonymized by limiting the surrounding contextual information. The following steps are taken:

- Distinguish potentially identifiable data points, e.g., named entities (names, dates, locations) and identifiable topics. Named entities are pseudonymized (see section 3.1.1).
- Write and/or review field notes and transcripts, highlighting each data point that may need de-identification.
- Edit by inserting blurred text, removing redacted text, or inserting summaries of large redactions:
 - Draft and insert blurred text: convert numerical data to an interval range, and replace labeled terms with superordinate categories, substituting specific text passages with more generalized text.
 - Bracket redacted text, removing potentially identifiable sections, and insert a summary with information on the key variables when possible in case of longer redactions.
- Review and discuss the edits in team. When possible or needed, discuss the redactions with participants, and consider their requests for de-identification or redactions (e.g., participants requesting removal of a recording or transcript from the data; participants allowing certain information to be retained in the texts but with specific anonymization strategies; etc.). If necessary, write memos (research notes) reporting participant requests concerning data dissemination (e.g., “you can keep this information but do not share this or that aspect of it”).

3.1.1 Pseudonymization and anonymization

A de-identification key, specifying replacements, aggregations, or removals, will be created and stored securely and separately from the anonymized data files.

Names of individuals

- *Names of participants*: after explaining the use of pseudonyms to the family, researchers invite them to choose a pseudonym for themselves and/or their children or partner, if they wish. Otherwise, pseudonyms are chosen by the researchers considering the characteristics of the name (e.g., origin, language, meaning). Pseudonyms are used directly in field notes and transcriptions whenever possible.

- *Names of other people within the family*: both pseudonymization and de-identification by subordinate category are considered, depending on the contextual information available (e.g., replacing with the relationship to the person). More specifically, using a subordinate category may become necessary when the participants may become identifiable or experience distress due to the possibility of identification – in such cases, we replace the name/identity with more general identifiers, such as “[participant]” or “[family member]”, as exemplified below. This is assessed on a case-by-case basis.
- *Names of other people outside the family (e.g., teachers, social workers)*: both pseudonyms and de-identification by subordinate category are considered, depending on contextual information (e.g., replacing with the relationship to the person). Pseudonyms are preferred when a person is known to the researchers and/or mentioned frequently by the family.

Example: a fictional family from Pakistan (AI-generated)

Info	Name	Pseudonymization	Anonymization options
42-year-old male from Pakistan; Fatima’s husband; father of 3; Muslim	Hassan Ali Khan <i>Hassan is a common Muslim name meaning "handsome" or "good," and Ali is a revered name in Islamic tradition. Khan is a common surname, historically used for rulers or leaders in South Asia.</i>	Zayd Noor <i>Zayd is a name meaning "growth" or "abundance," and Noor means "light" or radiance," symbolizing wisdom or a guiding figure.</i>	[BLURRED: Pakistani father] [BLURRED: Pakistani man in his 40s] [BLURRED: Muslim man] [BLURRED: man] [BLURRED: research participant] [REDACTED]
38-year-old woman from Pakistan; Hassan’s wife; mother of 3; Muslim	Fatima Bibi Khan <i>Fatima is a common name in Pakistan, rooted in Islamic tradition. Bibi is often used as a respectful title for women, meaning "lady" or "honorable woman." Khan, as mentioned, is the family surname.</i>	Sana Tariq <i>Sana means "radiance" or "brilliance" and is a popular name in Pakistan.</i>	[BLURRED: Pakistani mother] [BLURRED: Pakistani woman in her 30s] [BLURRED: Muslim woman] [BLURRED: woman] [BLURRED: research participant] [REDACTED]
Fatima and Hassan’s 5-year-old son; has 2 older siblings	Bilal Ahmed Khan <i>Bilal is a popular name in Pakistan, associated with the first muezzin in Islam, who is known for his beautiful call to prayer. Ahmed is a widely used name, meaning "highly praised."</i>	Omar Noor <i>Omar is the first name chosen by Hassan.</i>	[BLURRED: third-born child of Pakistani family] [BLURRED: 5-year-old boy] [BLURRED: 5-year-old] [BLURRED: boy] [BLURRED: child] [BLURRED: research participant] [REDACTED]
Hassan’s older sister and Bilal’s aunt; a traditional woman, who disagrees with the family’s educational decisions; does not participate in the	Zainab Raza <i>Zainab is a common and respected name in Pakistan, meaning "fragrant" or "aromatic." Raza is a common surname, meaning "contentment" or "approval," often associated with Islamic heritage.</i>	Samina Shaikh <i>Samina is a name that means "healthy" or "wholesome," and Shaikh is a surname that often denotes a person of leadership or respect, though it also indicates a</i>	[BLURRED: Omar’s aunt] [BLURRED: Hassan’s sister] [BLURRED: family member] [REDACTED]

research, but is frequently mentioned by Fatima		connection to religious or scholarly traditions.	
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Dates and numerical data

- Dates of key events: convert into range.

Locations and places

- *Names of schools:* the funding grant is public and there are many people who could identify the sites of the ethnography. For the purposes of data storage, locations and places recurring both as physical locations for meetings as well as those mentioned by the participants are pseudonymized. Anonymization strategies are considered in a case-by-case scenario and depend upon the disclosure of other contextual information (e.g., in a scientific publication on a related topic).

Example: fictional schools and locations in South Tyrol (AI-generated)

Type of location	Name	Pseudonymization	Anonymization
Primary school - German	Grundschule Am Waldrand <i>The name recalls the idea of a school located next to a forest, with quiet and natural surroundings.</i>	Wolfgang Grün <i>The name recalls nature and trees, with "Grün" meaning "Green" in German.</i>	[BLURRED: German primary school in a rural area] [BLURRED: German primary school] [BLURRED: Primary school] [BLURRED: School] [REDACTED]
Primary school - Italian	Scuola Primaria San Michele <i>The name of a saint recalls tradition and a sense of community.</i>	Scuola Primaria San Carlo <i>The name of another saint is chosen. In this case, the name is of the same gender.</i>	[BLURRED: Italian primary school in a town] [BLURRED: Italian primary school] [BLURRED: Primary school] [BLURRED: School] [REDACTED]
Neighborhood	Quartiere delle Vigne <i>This name evokes a connection to vineyards, and gives a serene, nature-filled feel.</i>	Quartiere della Valle <i>"Valle" suggests a valley and hints to a local area in a generic way.</i>	[BLURRED: neighborhood in the centre of a city in South Tyrol] [BLURRED: neighborhood of a city in South Tyrol] [BLURRED: neighborhood] [REDACTED]
Social place within a neighborhood	Centro Sociale delle Vigne <i>Named after the neighborhood "Quartiere delle Vigne".</i>	Centro Sociale della Valle <i>Named after the neighborhood "Quartiere Valle di Rosso".</i>	[BLURRED: social aggregation place located in a neighborhood in the centre of a city in South Tyrol] [BLURRED: social aggregation place in located in a city in South Tyrol] [BLURRED: social aggregation place] [REDACTED]

3.2 Storage and back-up

The data storage process will be as follows:

1. Upon initial collection, due to lack of internet access at the field sites, A3 and A4 data will be stored either in a physical notebook/paper format or on password-protected computers provided by Eurac. Audio recordings will be collected using digital audio recorders with SD disks provided by the partner institution.
2. As soon as possible, within 48 hours, these data (A3 and A4) will be transferred (directly, not via the internet) to the computer and immediately to SharePoint (which requires Microsoft Authenticator for access).
3. As soon as possible, within one month from the date of original data collection, pseudonyms will be applied to all data (textual replacement of names and/or blurring).
4. Excerpts of these de-identified data will be transferred to CAQDAS software for analysis (coding, transcription, etc.) and discussed in data interpretation sessions with other team members. CAQDAS software files will be shared on Eurac's OneDrive between members of the WP3 team (the Co-PI and PhD Student) and via the University of Innsbruck's online cloud, i.e., Fileshare (Seafile), for collaboration.
5. In order to carry out the overarching analyses and interpretation of the data, which is coordinated by the PI, files containing de-identified will be transferred to the partner institution (i.e., University of Innsbruck) via their secure server. A Joint Controller Agreement was signed between the two parties.
6. A copy of the data collected by Safà El Koura (PhD Student) during her fieldwork at Eurac Research will be transferred to the partner's secure server upon termination of her contract with Eurac (1st September 2025). As per the project timeline, we expect the fieldwork to continue at that time. Therefore, we anticipate that the anonymization/pseudonymization process of field notes, audio recordings, and interviews carried out by Safà El Koura will still be in process before, during, and after data are transferred to the other institution.
7. Raw data may be securely stored on Eurac Research's server until the end of the project. Before this period ends, the pseudonym key will be destroyed, and de-identification be implemented. Selections of A3 and A4 data (pseudonymized) will be stored on Eurac servers.

3.3 Folder structures and file naming

To ensure a well-organized and accessible archive of ethnographic research materials, all data related to a particular family is stored within a single main folder named after the family. This structured approach facilitates efficient retrieval and long-term data management.

3.3.1 Main Folder Structure

Each family has its own dedicated folder, labeled using the family's name, e.g., "Hannah". Within this main folder, field notes are stored. Each field note is a Word document corresponding to a single ethnographic visit, containing all the related observations, interviews, pictures, and transcripts of audio files. When aTrain was used, the software transcription output is stored separately in designated subfolders. The same applies to pictures.

- **Field notes.** These files follow the naming convention:
[Initials of researcher]_[Family name]_[Date]
 - Example: GA_Hannah_2025.06.13

3.3.2 Subfolders

Subfolders include:

- **Audio Recordings.** Each recorded interview or observation is saved as:
[Initial of researcher]_[Family name]_[Date]_audio_[Audio number]
 - Example: GA_Hannah_2025.06.13_audio_1
- **Photographs.** Each picture is saved as:
[Initial of researcher]_[Family name]_[Date]_[Picture number]_[Short description]
 - Example: GA_Hannah_2025.06.13_1_dinner
- **aTrain transcription output.** A dedicated subfolder within the main family folder holds all transcription data. Each transcription consists of a folder named identically to its corresponding audio file:
[Initial of researcher]_[Family name]_[Date]_audio_[Audio number]
 - Example: GA_Hannah_2025.06.13_audio_1

This unified folder structure ensures that all materials related to a single family are systematically archived in one location, maintaining coherence while allowing easy access to textual, audio, and transcription data.

4 Data documentation

4.1 Data consistency and quality control

Quality assurance for ethnographic data comes at several points and focuses on ensuring trustworthiness and rigor of qualitative research findings. The research team plans regular updates. Weekly meetings are held for reflection and identification of analytical themes, transcription conventions, data collection methods, etc. Synchronous data interpretation sessions are also organized by the partner institution. These collaborative sessions highlight and address any unconscious bias in data processing and analysis (i.e., credibility and reflexivity). In addition, participants will validate the field notes and transcripts and thus ensure data quality control (i.e., member checking). When possible, joint analysis of selected data with the participants will be carried out, either individually or in groups. These measures ensure that the data remains accurate, reliable, and reflective of the true nature of the research context, while also protecting the privacy of the participants. By engaging in regular review and involving participants in the validation process, the integrity and authenticity of the data are maintained.

4.1.1 Metadata

Metadata provides crucial information about the identities, spaces, and timings of the research, helping with organization, access, interpretation, and protection of participants' privacy. Researchers in WP3 regularly keep track of metadata in a .csv file stored in Eurac's secure OneDrive. The metadata file is organized based on ethnographic visits. Each ethnographic encounter, meeting, interview, or observation will count as one separate entry. For each entry, the researchers keep track of:

- The ethnographer
- The context, differentiating access to the field, from ethnography with families, interviews with other key informants, peer groups, and other types of events which may become relevant as the research evolves
- Location, date, and duration, recording where and when the data was collected, including specific locations and timestamps
- Participant information
- Key information about the event, using keywords to aid future retrieval
- Data types specifying in what forms data originated, i.e., field notes, audio, pictures, and transcriptions
- Associated files
- Other notes.

5 Data access

All data will be stored in SharePoint at Eurac Research which relies on Microsoft Authenticator for access. The folders on the Co-PI's desktop and on the server will be encrypted, and the passwords for encryption management will be stored securely by the PI and by the ICT department of Eurac. All files are automatically backed up to SharePoint as soon as the computer is connected to the internet and the VPN. Eurac is ISO certified -- Quality Management System (9001) and Information Security Management (27001).

5.1 Copyright and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR)

The EduLiM project staff follows Eurac Research rules on IPR and is conscious that the project generated data belongs to Eurac Research. At any time, any participant has the right to request access to their personal data, and to correct or delete that data, or to limit its processing. In addition, participant have the right to lodge a complaint with a supervisory authority. The processing of personal data is based on consent, and participants have the right to withdraw at any time and without consequences. The data subject may also exercise all other rights pursuant to current data protection regulations (art. 15 et seq. GDPR) by writing to the e-mail address: privacy@eurac.edu

5.2 Data access and sharing

We consider data access and sharing along the ends of a continuum which involves both internal data management and research outputs/dissemination. The understanding of data in ethnography and in the EduLiM project prioritizes context-rich, situated, and co-constructed knowledge. Following this perspective, there are currently no plans for making datasets open. As mentioned, EduLiM deals with a variety of personal data, some of which belong to special categories (art. 9 of the GDPR). Hence, data access will be restricted during the project to the Co-PI (Giorgia Andreolli) and the PhD Student (Safà El Koura). Following the establishment of a Joint Controller Agreement, data may be shared with the research team at the partner institution. Data may be accessed by supervisors at Eurac Research in case of unforeseen circumstances (see Section 5.3). The data, following the de-identification processes, may take different forms:

- Raw data, i.e., data in their full and original form
- Minimally de-identified data, i.e., data retaining rich contextual information
- Significantly de-identified data, i.e., data retaining as little contextual information as necessary
- Redacted, i.e., data omitted.

Except for raw data, all the other stages may include both pseudonymized and/or anonymized data. The Table below indicates the possibility of accessing and sharing each form of data according to different purposes.

	Raw data	Minimally de-identified	Significantly de-identified	Redacted
WP3 Data management*	Definitely will	Definitely will	Definitely will	Definitely will
WP3 Data collection and analysis**	Definitely will	Definitely will	Probably will	Probably won't
Data analysis sessions and exchanges with the project partner	Probably won't	Definitely will	Probably will	Probably won't
Dissemination in conferences, lectures, seminars	Definitely won't	Probably will	Definitely will	Definitely will
Dissemination in written reports, research articles, manuscripts, theses	Definitely won't	Probably will	Definitely will	Definitely will

Legenda:

Definitely will
Probably will
Probably won't
Definitely won't

*Refers to data collected, managed, and analyzed individually by each researcher in WP3.

**Refers to data collected, managed, and analyzed jointly by the researchers in the WP3.

5.3 Data access in case of staff changes

In case of unforeseen circumstances, the Co-PI's supervisors at Eurac Research (Institute for applied linguistic), namely Andrea Abel and Marta Guarda, may access data.

6 Data storage and preservation

6.1 Criteria for long-term preservation

Data will be archived for 10 years according to the following criteria:

- Compliance with confidentiality and privacy commitments as well as with what the participant has given their consent for
- Total de-identification and anonymization (large redactions included)
- Reuse value for the scientific community and secondary analysis only in cases where the researchers are directly involved.

7 Legal and ethical considerations

EduLiM follows the GDPR throughout the entire research process, including the consent, storage, and anonymization of personal data. However, there are no standardized ethical guidelines for the design of ethnographic research due to its inherent richness and complexity. In EduLiM, consent is approached as an ongoing process rather than a one-time event or checkbox exercise. This approach involves continuous discussion and negotiation with participants during the project, reflecting a commitment to process orientation and enhanced ethical reflexivity. EduLiM adheres to the regulations of the Ethics Review Board at Eurac Research. Although legal and ethical oversight was sought, it was not possible to submit the project for review due to the simultaneous establishment of the review board and the onset of EduLiM. The following documentation was produced:

- Ethical self-assessment
- GDPR questionnaire for research projects
- Data protection impact assessment (DPIA)
- Consent form for participants, including information notice and privacy statement
- Joint controller agreement

Legal and ethical supervision

- Hanna Pfattner, Eurac Legal Office, hanna.pfattner@eurac.edu
- Sophia Schönthaler, Researcher at the Center for Migration and Diversity at Eurac Research and administrator of the Eurac Research Ethics Review Board, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2096-7097>

8 Resources and costs

Researchers in WP3 work on data collection, transcriptions, analysis, and dissemination. Personnel costs related to these activities have been budgeted and funded. Eurac Research promotes Open Science practices and provides necessary infrastructures for data management. Staff laptops and the OneDrive/SharePoint cloud storage are provided by Eurac Research. Thus, they do not entail any additional cost. Eurac Research IT provides support for setting up the data access and security protocols. Audio recorders are purchased by the partner institution and borrowed during the whole period of data collection.